

that of the checks. The results of the present experiment suggest that improvement of parental lines is needed for F₁ hybrids to show further superiority over checks. □

Yield depression in F₂ hybrids of rice *Oryza sativa* L.

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We evaluated four F₂ rice hybrids and their corresponding F₁ parents with IR54, a recommended pureline variety, as check in a replicated yield trial in 1983 dry season at IRR. Twenty-one-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing and one seedling per hill, in 5.0- × 3.4-m plots, NPK was applied at 120-50-30 kg/ha.

The F₁ hybrids and IR54 flowered relatively earlier and were more uniform in flowering and plant height than the F₂.

Yield and yield depression in F₂ rice hybrids and the corresponding F₁ hybrids.

Hybrid, check	Yield (t/ha)		Yield depression ^a (%) in F ₂
	F ₁ hybrid	F ₂ hybrid	
IET3257/IR2797-105-2-2-3	8.3	6.6	-21**
IET3257/IR54	8.3	6.8	-19**
IR11248-242-3-2/IR15324-117-3-2	7.7	6.6	-14**
IR1124&242-3-2/IR19672-19-3-3-1	8.2	6.8	-18**
IR54 (check)	6.7		

^a ** = significant at 1% level.

Flowering took about 15 d between 99 and 114 d after sowing in IET3257/IR2797 and 12 d for the 3 other F₂ hybrids. Uneven F₂ plant height, flowering, and maturity were due to segregation of genes for those traits.

Grain yield was determined from 5 m². Because of staggered F₂ maturity, plants were harvested on two dates. Grain yield was adjusted to 14% moisture, and reported in t/ha. Yield depression in F₂ was computed as (F₂ - F₁) ÷ F₁ and expressed as a percentage. Statistical significance of the difference was tested using LSD.

Yield depression (see table) in F₂ ranged from 14 to 21% and was significant in all the hybrids. However, the F₂ yields were comparable with those of IR54. The highest yield depression in F₂ was observed in the combination IET3257/IR2797. The same combination had also expressed the highest yield heterosis in F₁. Therefore, to exploit the yield advantage of F₁ rice hybrids, it would be necessary to sow fresh F₁ seed every year. Sowing F₂ seed (harvest made from F₁ rice hybrid) would significantly reduce yield. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization TISSUE CULTURE

Response of rice anthers to callus induction and plant regeneration

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Anther culture can speed genetic improvement of crops by increasing selection efficiency within a short time. We studied the response of anthers to culture medium.

Cold shocked anthers of 40 boro varieties, breeding lines, and F₂ plants were cultured in N6 (for japonica) and modified H5 and SK-8 (for indica and indica/japonica) media at early to mid-uninucleate stage of microspore development. Of the 18 lines that produced calli, 2 were japonicas, 1 was indica/japonica, and 15 were indicas. Anther

Rice anther variability in inducing callus and plant differentiation, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Variety or line	Type	Anthers inoculated (no.)	Induction		Differentiation ^a (%)		
			No.	%	Roots only	Albino plants	Green plants
Zhing hua-2	japonica	270	60	22	50	18	0
Zhing hua-5	japonica	600	222	37	30	37	25
BG96-3/J2	indica	311	23	7	33	33	17
BR161-2B-58	indica	262	6	2	60	0	0
Guichao No. 2	indica	368	2	0	100	0	0
Habiganj Boro-VI	indica	155	39	25	50	30	0
Habiganj Boro VIII	indica	162	56	35	45	10	0
IR40	indica	330	11	3	57	14	0
IR19660-11	indica	215	3	1	33	0	0
IR19660-311	indica	404	68	13	70	15	5
IR19090-24-5-3-1-1	indica	230	1	0	100	0	0
Pajam	indica/japonica	1825	82	4	48	27	11
Zenith	indica	230	3	1	67	0	0
BR4228 (F ₂)	indica	840	54	6	37	35	10
BR4229 (F ₂)	indica	295	8	3	60	40	0
BR4249 (F ₂)	indica	480	15	3	50	20	0
BR4251 (F ₂)	indica	455	3	1	100	0	0
BR4252 (F ₂)	indica	575	12	2	50	20	0
Total (induction)		8007	668	8.34	-	-	-
Weighted av (differentiation) ^a		-	-	-	48.3	23.1	7.7

^a Based on number of calli transferred for differentiation.